

CASE REPORT

A case report on managing horizontally fractured central incisor

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Abstract

Traumatic dental injuries are the main reason behind most dental crises. Due to its placement in the arch and labially proclined nature, maxillary central incisors are thought to be the most vulnerable to crown fractures brought by dental trauma. The horizontal crown fracture, which is more frequently observed, usually affects the maxillary anterior region and among young patients. This case reports on managing horizontal crown fractures with pulp exposure on an 11-year-old male patient that was successfully treated by endo-restoration therapy and the use of Porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crowns in order to restore the tooth's shape and function. Endo-restoration therapy is the major therapeutic option for complicated crown fractures brought by dental trauma. Its retention is improved through an endodontic procedure, followed by a post and core insertion in the root canal which would serve as an abutment for the PFM crown. These treatments would then recover the tooth's form and function which boosts the patient's confidence. This concludes that the use of Endo-restoration therapy, post and core, as well as PFM crowns can restore normal function, esthetics, and self-confidence for anterior teeth with horizontal crown fractures and pulp exposure.

Keywords dental crown, tooth fracture, root canal therapy, gingivoplasty, post and core technique, dental porcelain

1 | Introduction

"Fracture including dentin, cement, and pulp" is the definition of a root fracture. The middle third of the root is where horizontal root fracture most

frequently occurs, whereas the coronal and apical thirds are only very infrequently affected.¹ The location of the maxillary central incisors in the dental arch may be the reason why they are more vulnerable to damage.

The maxillary lateral incisors come next, then the mandibular incisors. The compression zone labially, lingually, and/or palatally is affected by frontal pressures, which causes root fracture, causing the root to be split into coronal and apical fragments.² This may cause the supporting periodontal tissues to

frequently necessary for cervical third root fractures. There is only one course of action when the coronal fragment exhibits extreme mobility, extraction. Middle-third root fractures have a decent prognosis.⁴ When the coronal fragment is misplaced, realigning the fragments first is the best course of

Figure 1. Pre-operative (A) photograph and (B) radiograph

become traumatized, eventually causing the root pieces to shift. Correct root fracture diagnosis requires a thorough clinical and radiographic investigation.³ A doctor must assess the pulp vitality and the coronal fragment's movement. The apical and coronal pieces are distinguished radiographically by a radiolucent line.

The position, mobility, and vitality of the tooth all affect how a horizontal root fracture is treated. Apical third fractures typically show little movement and don't need any medical attention. Root extraction is

action, followed by stabilizing them so that the periodontal tissues may heal around them. Fiber posts with a tooth-colored finish have been created in response to the growing demand for aesthetics. These posts can be used to hold the two broken root segments together when paired with bonding chemicals and composite resins.⁵

This case study demonstrated how dental trauma-caused crown fractures of teeth were treated by exposing the pulp and using endodontic therapy in order to restore the tooth's form and function.

Table 1. Treatment plan

1st visit	Oral prophylaxis
	Periapical x-ray
2nd visit	Root canal treatment: Establish working length and irrigation of canal
3rd visit	Shaping the canal
	Dressing
	Filling of Calcium Hydroxide
4th visit	Canal Obturation
5th visit	Removal of gutta percha through post and core drill
	Preparation of wax pattern for post and core
6th visit	Installation of post and core
	Gingivoplasty
7th visit	Crown shade selection
	Installation of provisional crown
8th visit	Installation of Porcelain-fused-to-metal crown

2 | Case presentation section

An 11-year-old patient presents to the dental clinic with his parents with the chief complaint, “Dili mi ganahan sa suggested treatment sa una nga dentist na ibridge, unsa pay lain pwede buhaton? (We are not satisfied with the treatment suggested by our prior dentist which is to do bridging, what other treatment options can we consider?)”. Patient has a fractured upper left central incisor due to trauma from an accident where the patient slipped and fell face forward. Upon examination, the periapical x-ray revealed a history of root canal therapy which served as an immediate treatment for the patient by his first dentist. Slight reduction of tooth surface was also done in preparation for the fabricated acrylic crown of the upper left lateral incisor. The patient's medical history was non-contributory.

Clinical examination revealed a horizontally fractured central incisor (#21) and a slightly reduced enamel surface on the adjacent tooth (Figure 1-A).

Radiographic examination disclosed a periapical lesion, and inadequate radiopacity from the gutta-percha and cement on the root canal of tooth #21 (Figure 1-B). The fracture can be observed on the cervical third of the crown. Root length was assessed to be adequate enough to achieve a 1:1 crown-root ratio following a post and core procedure.

2.1. Diagnosis

Cervically Fractured Central Incisor (#21)

2.2. Proposed Treatment

Root Canal Therapy, Gingivoplasty, Post and Core, and PFM Crown were done (Table 1).

Diagnostic X-ray was done to determine the quality of the root canal and other dental problems such as the extent of trauma. Upon observation, there was a lack of radiopacity from the gutta percha and cement on the root canal therefore re-RCT was recommended. Root canal treatment was performed on tooth #21 to determine its working length and irrigation channel, as well as canal shaping, dressing, calcium hydroxide filling, and canal obturation. Removal of gutta-percha was also done through

a post and core drill. Preparation of wax pattern was made and installation of post and core was carried out. Gingivoplasty was then performed to raise the abutment height. Selection of crown shade and placement of a provisional crown then followed and lastly, the PFM crown was installed. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. (A) Re-root canal, (B) wax pattern, (C) device fabricated, (D) installation of post and core, (E) gingivoplasty, and (F) placement of a provisional crown.

2.3. Prognosis

Good. The patient has adequate periodontal support, good oral hygiene, no bad habits, and fast healing due to young age.

3 | Discussion

Dental trauma after a permanent anterior tooth fracture is one of the most frequently met oral health

problems. The negative impact on the esthetics, speech, and masticatory functions is significantly attributed to this trauma as well as the psychology of both the patient and the parents, affecting the overall personality and daily life of an individual.⁶ Dental trauma such as tooth (crown) fracture should not be treated by tooth extraction in the young permanent tooth in the anterior area⁷ for it leads to bone loss in the area and compromises future implant therapy as a treatment.⁸

The pulp of tooth #21 was involved in the case presented hence, root canal treatment was performed to control the inflammation and manage the pain. For the reason that the amount of tooth structure remaining was nominal, a custom-made cast post and core were adjudicated to be suitable for the case. Endodontically treated teeth are usually restored with post support and retention for restoration when the remaining tooth structure cannot provide adequate support and retention for restoration. It has been reported that the fracture resistance of endodontically treated teeth is mainly dependent on the amount of remaining tooth structure and adhesive surface, the quality of adhesion, and the type of post since posts increase the fracture resistance of the root, especially in the absence of a full crown.⁹ Cast posts confirm the canal morphology and can be used in

all types of canal configurations- oval or elliptical. Using cast posts a slight change in core angulation can be done thereby they can be used for correcting proclined teeth unlike other prefabricated posts.¹⁰ Cast metal posts have exposed higher survival rates which are over ten years.¹¹

To increase the abutment height, gingivoplasty was performed after installing a cast metal post and core. The subgingival fragment had been elevated in the axial direction utilizing an edgewise fixed appliance. Optimum esthetic was accomplished when the restoration was performed after the fracture line had lifted above the level of the gingival line.¹² In the case presented, porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) was then installed after performing the gingivoplasty giving enough space for the crown to be installed. Porcelain Fused to Metal (PFM) crowns have been considered the gold standard for the repair of damaged teeth. PFM crowns have good mechanical properties, satisfactory esthetic results, and an acceptable biological quality needed for periodontal health.¹³ The use of metal posts is justified by various studies showing their superior fracture resistance.¹⁴ The permanent restoration was delayed until it was ensured that the dentogingival junction is located entirely on cementum by the passive eruption, to

avoid esthetic discrepancy at a later time.¹⁵

Through this, they can support damaged teeth that would otherwise be lost or extracted and can last a lifetime with proper care. This can also reduce tooth sensitivity, with most patients reporting very little tooth sensitivity after the treatment. Because they are custom made to match the adjacent teeth down to the shape and shade of the restoration, it would also help the child boost his confidence in smiling beautifully. Hence, it is strongly advised to use PFM crowns in the patient's case to ensure that the damaged tooth remains aesthetically pleasing while also having a strong structure to perform its primary function.

4 | Conclusions

A well-constructed interdisciplinary approach can help save a tooth that might otherwise be removed completely. In this case, the use of endo-restoration therapy, post and core, as well as PFM crowns can restore normal function, esthetics, and self-confidence for anterior teeth with horizontal crown fractures and pulp exposure. When dentist-patient relationship and accurate estimation of prognosis are carried out with forethought and purpose, the chances of successful treatment planning are enhanced. It is often appropriate to

also execute recall visits to ensure good long-term outcomes.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist.

All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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